

The Ma_MISSION Processors

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Abstract

This manuscript is the **Software User Manual** of the `Ma_MISSION_Processors` program, in details it will describe the installation procedure, the configuration file and how the program can be used to generate the expected outputs from the raw data from ROCC TM2Raw processor.

Keywords

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1. Introduction

With "processor" we intend the program that perform some task inside the ROCC (Rover Operations Control Center) pipeline. The `Ma_MISSION` team is involved into the production of the processors to perform the calibration of the raw data: the start point of all the `Ma_MISSION` processors are the raw data, namely the data that the instrument on the Rover will produce; the raw data are extracted from the telemetry data by a first processing, the development of this first processor is the responsibility of the ROCC, `Ma_MISSION` team are not involved into.

In [1] is described in details the pipeline developed in ROCC and how the `Ma_MISSION` processors are involved. While in [2] it is provided the format specification of telemetry data during the operations by `Ma_MISSION`.

This document describes how to use the processors where the `Ma_MISSION` team is involved, in particular it will describe the calibration processors: for calibration we intend the transformation of the data from the instrument (in digital number, due to the quantization of the sensor data, for example) into physical meaning of the data. Also, we interpret as calibration

the transformation of the binary data into an equivalent human readable format, that represent the interpretation of the data from the instrument.

There are four processors (they will be describe in section 2) that are run by a single execution program: the execution program name is `Ma_MISSION_Processors` and it manages a single configuration file in XML format: it is an important part of program, that will be present an example in the Appendix A.

During the elaboration, the program will generate a log file that will report the status of the processing data, a look to this file may help the final user to interpretate the right execution of the programs and if it was produced one or more errors.

In the Paragraph ?? will describe the installation procedure of `Ma_MISSION_Processors` in a Linux Operative System with RPM (Red Hat Package Manager), there is not an explicit link to a particular distribution, but as wrote in [1] we had choose the Centos GNU/Linux distribution, a very constraint is the 64-bits platform.

In the Figure 1 there is a schema of conceptual connections: the program is divided into four processors (see the green box), the Primary Products in input is colored in yellow rounded box while the output products, for each processors, are represented by a red box; the Calibration and Preflight data products are represented by a violet box (the definition of this products are described into [1]). With a pink box it is represented `Ma_MISSION_Processors` and its outputs: the Logs file, the DN (Digital Number) file and the Primary Products calibrated.

`Ma_MISSION_Processors` contains also an PDS4 library that is aligned to the documentation [3], that it was wrote to manage the input and the output in PDS4 format.

Figure 1. The Ma_MISS_Processors schema and connections.

2. Ma_MISS processors program

Ma_MISS_Processors is a shell program that can be able to run into Linux operative system, there isn't a Graphical User Interface for the program. You can see the all settable parameters of the program by using the following shell command:

```
> Ma_MISS_Processors -h
```

where > is the command prompt; the user can looking to the man page delivered with the processors. The program are developed into the Bash environment, but can be run on every favorite shell.

The fondamental shell's parameter is `-config_file` and, as explains the name, set the file name of XML config file (see A to see an example). All the parameters listed into config file can be **overwritten** by setting the relative shell parameter.

The `-config_file` belongs to the *management parameters* that are used to handle the primary function of the program. There are also the *folder* and *calibration parameters* that are used to set some usefull setting (like the input and/or output parameters and the auxiliary files) that the program will use to exect his task. All the possible shell parameters are

listed in the following paragraphs.

Management parameters

- `-config_file` set the configuration file, this is a fondamental parameter that must be always set, if not give as input parameters an error will be generate and the program will stop.
- `-log_level` is the level of log: 1=INFO, 2=WARNING, 3=ERROR, 4=FATAL, other number DEBUG
- `-processor_number` run a specific Ma_MISS processors, see the following paragraphs for a description of the possible values.
- `-version` get the version of the program.
- `-dn` must be used as science debug function, it not must used into the ROCC pipeline because the program (with `-dn`) will produce only file not archiviable in PDS4 format.

Folder parameters

- `-input_folder` set the folder where the program expect to find the RAW data (in PDS4 format as established into [1]).

- in `-output_folder` the program will produce the PDS4 calibrated files as established into [1].
- a log folder can be set by the parameter `-log_folder`.

Calibration parameters

In [1] was established seven calibration and pre-flight product, all are formalized into PDS4 format to archive it. These are seven files ASCII plus seven XML label that describes the contents of the data. `Ma_MISSION_PROCESSORS` can have access to the seven calibration and pre-flight product by defining seven variable: all the variable's name are formalize as established into [1]. The root name for the calibration and pre-flight product is `"-mis_cal_"` following with a number with two digits. Here the list of the seven variable:

- `-mis_cal_01`: Wavelength values of the 500 channels of the instrument focal plane
- `-mis_cal_02`: Spectrometer transfer function (STF)
- `-mis_cal_03`: Optical Rod Transmittance
- `-mis_cal_04`: Illumination source
- `-mis_cal_05`: Calibration curves used to calibrated the housekeeping parameters
- `-mis_cal_06`: Additional parameters used for the calibration procedures (e.s. F-number of optical system)
- `-mis_cal_07`: Sensor health

2.1 The processors

As reported in [1], the number of processors of `Ma_MISSION_PROCESSORS` are four and each of them can run with `-processor_number`; in details, the possible values of this parameters are reported in the follow. The default value is 2 that means if the program will run without parameters the processor 2 will be executed.

The values of `-processor_number` are:

- 2: run the science processor
- 3: run the housekeeping processor
- 4: the acknowledges, events and emergency processor will be executed
- 5: the diagnostic processor will analyze and update the sensor health products

See the Figure 1 for details of input and output for each processor and the [1] for an description of each processor, here was reported only a sintetic description to link a number to a processor.

To perform the own task, `Ma_MISSION_PROCESSOR` need a configuration file (for detail see the paragraph 3), where some variables are set to be used by the program, two of these variables are the input and the output folder.

`Ma_MISSION_PROCESSOR` scans the input folder to catch the relative RAW data and performs the calibration, producing

the CALIBRATED data into the output folder. Each processors manage different Primary Product as describe in to [1], and generate different Calibrated Primary Product.

In the log folder will be produced a log file (with the time stamp in the filename) where there are a report about the execution: the granularity of the report is guided by another variable inside the configuration file: `log_level`.

Note that if in the `-input_folder` there are RAW data that didn't match the `-processor_number`, the program will not generate nothing and will not report any errors.

3. Configuration file

The configuration file consist in a XML file format [see appendix A], containing five settings.

1. `ma_miss_calibration_data` is a list of the calibration data, see [1].
2. `input` is the folder where the processor waits for the RAW data input.
3. `output` is the directory where the processor writes the output data (PDS4 products).
4. `log_level` is the level of log: 1=INFO, 2=WARNING, 3=ERROR, 4=FATAL, other number DEBUG
5. `log_folder` is the folder where the processor writes the log of its execution.

The position where the calibration data are stored in the file system is contained into the `folder` attribute of the tag `ma_miss_calibration_data`, that contains a list of the files for the pre-flight and calibration data products; the tags of this list of products must have the same name formalized into [1] but in lower case format.

`Ma_MISSION_PROCESSORS` has access to the configuration file by using the shell parameter `-config_file` as described into 1.

An example of configuration file is reported in Appendix A, as you can see there is the flexibility to use environment variable inside the configuration file: in the example is used the variable `HOME_MA_MISSION_PROCESSORS`. The usage of environmental variable into the configuration file is not mandatory, by recommended.

All the settings parameters, that are wrote into the configuration file, can be overwritten by the shell parameters (described into 1).

The parameter `ma_miss_calibration_data` can not be overwritten, these because there are direct acces to the calibration and pre-flight parameters by using the *Calibration parameters* described into 1.

References

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- [3] NASA. PDS4 data dictionary. *Abridged - Version 1.13.0.0*, 2021. https://pds.nasa.gov/datastandards/documents/dd/current/PDS4_PDS_DD_1D00.html.

A. An example of configuration file

Here it is reported an example of configuration file; it is used the enviromental variable \$HOME_MA_MISS only to stress that it is not needed to link the varius folders to an absolute path.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<ma_miss_processors>
  <ma_miss_calibration_data folder="$HOME_MA_MISS/calib">
    <mis-cal-01>mis_raw_calib_wavelengths.xml</mis-cal-01>
    <mis-cal-02>mis_raw_calib_stf.xml</mis-cal-02>
    <mis-cal-03>mis_raw_calib_tau.xml</mis-cal-03>
    <mis-cal-04>mis_raw_calib_lampirradiance.xml</mis-cal-04>
    <mis-cal-05>mis_raw_calib_calibrationcurves.xml</mis-cal-05>
    <mis-cal-06>mis_raw_calib_extraparameters.xml</mis-cal-06>
    <mis-cal-07>mis_raw_calib_sensorhealth.xml</mis-cal-07>
  </ma_miss_calibration_data>
  <input>$HOME_MA_MISS/input</input>
  <output>$HOME_MA_MISS/output</output>
  <log_level>1</log_level>
  <log_folder>$HOME_MA_MISS/logs</log_folder>
</ma_miss_processors>
```

B. Installation procedure

To install Ma_MISS_Processor the user need two RPM archives: one for the processors that contains the executable, the man page and the present manual; an another archive that contains the calibrations pre flight products. All the RPMs are installed by using the following command:

```
> sudo rpm -i <filename.rpm>
```

C. Test of the processors

One of the deployed kickoff RMP contains a set of data to test the porcessors on ROCC pipeline (namde Frankenstein dataset); the contents of the package are described in the README.md file within the package itself. These data allow to exercise the functions of processors 2, 3 and 4.

To install the Frankestein data use the following procedure:

1. install the Frankestein rmp archive (> sudo rmp -i <fielname.rpm>)
2. create the folder \$HOME/ma_miss/test_data with the commands:

```
> mkdir ma_miss
> mkdir ma_miss/test_data
```

The installation process will create the folder `/opt/ma_miss/test_data` with the Frankenstein dataset. The output folder, present into `/opt/ma_miss/test_data/output` folder generated, contains the output generated by the processors on the following machine:

- CPU: Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-3770 CPU @ 3.40GHz
- RAM: 20 GB

To produce the output folder the following commands was run on the previous configuration:

```
> time Ma_MISS.Processors -processor_number <NUM> -config_file Ma_MISS.processors_configuration.xml
```

the `<NUM>` is the number of processor to run: was run first the processor 3, following 2 and 4. The order of the launch of the processors in this case matters: there are only HK in the input dataset with the science case, there isn't the case with single HK acquisition. In this situation if we run the processor 2 and after the processor 3, the last overwrites the link between the HK and the science data. **This must be a guideline, run first the processor 3 and after the processor 2.**

Using the `time` program on linux operative system we estimated the execution time of the processors on the dataset provided, the table 1 reports the results of `time` command.

<NUM>	Real [s]	User [s]	Sys [s]
2	3.085	1.808	1.419
3	1.126	1.035	0.198
4	0.025	0.013	0.012

Table 1. Ma_MISS.Processors execution time results from `time` command, run on the Frankenstein dataset

Here is reported the description of the time in the table:

Real is wall clock time - time from start to finish of the call. This is all elapsed time including time slices used by other processes and time the process spends blocked (for example if it is waiting for I/O to complete).

User is the amount of CPU time spent in user-mode code (outside the kernel) within the process. This is only actual CPU time used in executing the process. Other processes and time the process spends blocked do not count towards this figure.

Sys is the amount of CPU time spent in the kernel within the process. This means executing CPU time spent in system calls within the kernel, as opposed to library code, which is still running in user-space. Like 'user', this is only CPU time used by the process. See below for a brief description of kernel mode (also known as 'supervisor' mode) and the system call mechanism.

To elaborate the Frankenstein dataset the processor 2 spend about 2 seconds: this dataset contains 156 point of Ma_MISS spectra; for a big dataset, a ring with about 765 points for example, the processor spend about 10 seconds. For a column in high resolution mode there are 974 points, the processor could execute the calibration in 12 seconds.

D. ERRORS CODE

The following tables reports the errors code of the processors:

ID errors	Description	Solution
0	Process terminated successfully	Regular ending of Ma_MISS Processors
1	Configuration file not found and not all parameters were passed through shell	Provide a configuration file or set ALL program arguments by shell
2	Impossible to create the folder	Check S.O., for example the privileges in the log folder, in any case see the specific message in the standard error
3	Impossible to create the log file	Check S.O., for example the privileges in the log folder, in any case see the specific message in the standard error
4	Provided an empty input folder	Copy the files to process into the input
5	Unknown ID of processor	Provide a right processor ID in the range 2:5